

Historical Growth Rates of Food Grains Under Five-Year Planning in India

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Abstract

It is evident that the growth of Indian agricultural sector has been gradually declining its contribution to GDP over the period of time. Population of Indian economy has been continuously increasing and demand for food grains also increasing. In order to meet the increased demand for food articles India was introduced Green Revolution during the planning period. The five years planning was taken many initiatives to increase the food grains production in order to increase the growth of agricultural sector. This paper attempted to evaluate the real picture about the historical growth rates of food grain production during the five year planning period.

Introduction

Green Revolution is the time period to achieve rapid increase in the agricultural production in history of Indian agriculture under the five year planning period. During the independence period India was succeeded in production of food grains at the amount of 55 million tons. It is earmarking that as a result of implementations of many programs under five year planning the growth of food production was raised to 260 million tons by 2013-13 and it was the positive trends in Indian economy.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this paper is to examine the historical growth rates of food grains in India during five year planning period especially form 8th planning to 12th planning period.

Historical Growth Rates of Food Grains

Table 1

Planning Period	Year	Cereals				Pulses	Total Food Grains (Million tonnes)
		Rice	Wheat	Coarse Cereals	Total (2 to 4)		
8th Five Year Plan	1992-93	72.86	57.21	36.59	166.66	12.82	179.48
	1993-94	80.30	59.84	30.82	170.96	13.30	184.26
	1994-95	81.81	65.77	29.88	177.46	14.04	191.50
	1995-96	76.98	62.10	29.03	168.11	12.31	180.42
	1996-97	81.73	69.35	34.11	185.19	14.24	199.43

9th Five Year Plan	1997-98	82.54	66.35	30.40	179.29	13.83	193.12
	1998-99	86.08	71.29	31.33	188.70	14.91	203.61
	1999-00	89.68	76.37	30.34	196.39	13.41	209.80
	2000-01	84.98	69.68	31.08	185.74	11.07	196.81
	2001-02	93.34	72.77	33.37	199.48	13.37	212.85
10th Five Year Plan	2002-03	71.82	65.76	26.07	163.65	11.13	174.78
	2003-04	88.53	72.16	37.60	198.28	14.91	213.19
	2004-05	83.13	68.64	33.46	185.23	13.13	198.36
	2005-06	91.79	69.35	34.07	195.22	13.38	208.60
	2006-07	93.36	75.81	33.92	203.08	14.20	217.28
11th Five Year Plan	2007-08	96.69	78.57	40.75	216.01	14.76	230.78
	2008-09	99.18	80.68	40.04	219.90	14.57	234.47
	2009-10	89.09	80.80	33.55	203.45	14.66	218.11
	2010-11	95.98	86.87	43.40	226.25	18.24	244.49
	2011-12	105.30	94.88	42.01	242.20	17.09	259.29
12th Five Year Plan	2012-13	105.24	93.51	40.04	238.79	18.34	257.13
	2013-14	106.65	95.85	43.29	245.79	19.25	265.04
	2014-15	105.48	86.53	42.86	234.87	17.15	252.02
	2015-16	104.41	92.29	38.52	235.22	16.35	251.57
	2016-17	109.70	98.51	43.77	251.98	23.13	275.11
Total		2276.65	1910.94	890.30	5077.90	373.59	5451.50

Source: Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare, Government of India.

Graph-1: Historical Growth Rates of Food Grains during 8th Five Years Planning in India

The graph-1 shows that, the food grain production during 8th five year planning was rising continually at the rate of 3.606 percent per annum. It indicates that under 8th five year planning the food grains production was increased every year by 176.2 million tons. The 8th five year planning was achieved a historical increased growth in production of food grains by putting a continuous effort.

Graph 2 Historical Growth Rates of Food Grains during 9th Five Years Planning in India

The graph-2 shows that, the production of food grains under 9th planning was increasing continuously at the rate of 3.266 percent annum. From this one can understand that each year the food grains production has been increasing by 193.44million tons during the observed period of time. It is evident from the graph-2 that the 9th five year planning was made an outstanding effort in increasing the food grains during this five years period of time.

Graph 3 Historical Growth Rates of Food Grains during 10th Five Years Planning in India

The graph-3 depicts the annual growth rates of the production food grains under 10th five year planning period and it was increasing incessantly at the rate of 8.041 percent per annum. It is evident form the study that each year the food grains production has been increasing by 178.32 million tons during the experiential period of time. It is obvious from the graph-3 that the 10th five year planning was put a due effort in increasing the food grains during this five years period of time.

Graph 4: Historical Growth Rates of Food Grains during 11th Five Years Planning in India

It is also imperative to assess the effort made by 11th five year planning about the performance of production of food grains in India and is presented in graph-4. As it is depicted in the graph-4 it can be come to the conclusion that this planning has really struggled to increase the level of production food grains at the rate 6.704 percent per annum. It means that during 11th five year planning in India the production of food grains has been increased by 217.32 million tonnes. It is a positive growth of food grains in the economy.

Graph 5 Historical Growth Rates of Food Grains during 12th Five Years Planning in India

As it is presented in the graph-5 during 12th five year planning the production of food grains was increased positively as depicted by the trend line. It can be concluded that the food grains production was increased at the rate of 2.249 percent per annum. It means the production of food grains was increased by 253.43 million tonnes. Indian economy has made an imperative effort to increase the level of food grains over the period of time.

Findings of the Study

1. It is found that during 8th five year planning the food grains production was increased by 176.2 million tons in each year.
2. It is also found that each year the food grains production has been increased by 193.44 million tons during the 9th five year planning period of time.
3. It is marked from the study that every year the food grains production was increasing by the amount of 178.32 million tons during 10th five year planning period of time.
4. The study found that during 11th five year planning food grains production was augmented by the quantity of 217.32 million tonnes.
5. It is also found that the production of food grains was increased by 253.43 million tonnes during 12th five year planning period of time.

Conclusion

This study has evaluated the trends in the historical growth rates of food grains production during five year planning in India and came to the conclusion that, India has made an outstanding performance in increasing the food grains from 8th five year planning to 12th five year planning and there is a positive growth in the production of food grains.

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